

Group Size Shapes Interactions in Confined Minimal Active Biological Collectives.

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We demonstrate that group size reshapes the effective interaction network in confined biological collectives. Using minimal groups of the shrimp *Neocaridina davidi* ($N = 2, 3, 4$) as a representative nonequilibrium system, we reconstruct the asymmetric coupling matrix via an inverse asymmetric Ising model. This mapping is physically enabled by thigmotactic behavior, which restricts trajectories to a discrete decision space, allowing for a maximum-entropy description appropriate for steady states characterized by broken detailed balance.

Our analysis reveals a structured progression with increasing group size: mean coupling strength undergoes social screening, while heterogeneity, structural frustration, and nonreciprocal asymmetry emerge as defining architectural features. Group-size identity is encoded in a subspace orthogonal to the global coupling scale and statistical volatility.

Furthermore, the eigenvalue spectrum signals a stationary log-probability distribution in which collective rotational order is amplified while statistical barriers between configurations are lowered, thereby expanding the repertoire of accessible states. Confinement thus drives a well-defined architectural transition from simple reciprocal coordination toward a complex, heterogeneous, and nonreciprocal nonequilibrium steady state.

I. INTRODUCTION

Collective animal motion exhibits universal ordering principles, whereby local interactions among moving individuals produce coherent global patterns reminiscent of architectural crossovers in statistical physics [1, 2]. This analogy is grounded in simple theoretical models that demonstrate spontaneous symmetry breaking and macroscopic states resembling equilibrium systems [3, 4]. For instance, escape behavior in ants illustrates symmetry breaking: an isotropic state transitions into a coherent directional flow [5].

However, these minimal models provide only partial insight, as real biological collectives operate far from equilibrium, driven by continuous energy input, environmental constraints, and social coordination [6–8]. From a physical perspective, these organisms function as active particles that harness internal energy for persistent self-propulsion. When subjected to spatial confinement, this directed motion restricts the accessible configuration space and breaks detailed balance at the single-agent level [9], giving rise to

complex collective flows [10]. In biological systems, this boundary influence is often amplified by thigmotaxis—a wall-following tendency common across taxa.

To investigate these mechanisms, we employ collectives of the crustacean *Neocaridina davidi* as a representative model system, observing how geometric confinement channels interacting agents into dense, near-boundary flows [10, 11]. Such boundary-driven organization mirrors collective rotating states observed in confined active Brownian particles [12], where the dimensional reduction behaviorally enforced by thigmotaxis restricts trajectories to a binary decision space. At this coarse-grained level, the dynamics map onto Ising-like spin models [13], where the persistent violation of detailed balance seeds the sustained probability currents underlying the nonequilibrium steady-state (NESS) architecture. Analogous coordination motifs in other taxa [14, 15] suggest that such flows represent universal navigation principles, providing a robust experimental platform for investigating the nonequilibrium statistical mechanics of confined active collectives.

We investigate the fundamental lower bounds of collective nonreciprocity at the minimal viable scale ($N = 2, 3, 4$), aiming to uncover the universal architectural rules that precede large-scale flocking. In this geometry, higher densities trigger kinetic arrest due to crowding, fundamentally suppressing the exploratory dynamics required for inference. This low- N regime therefore constitutes

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a tractable, low-dimensional manifold for isolating the core interaction mechanisms that seed coordinated steady states. We examine how confinement induces non-trivial phenomena within these sparse groups, such as interaction screening and emergent structural robustness, and evaluate whether these minimal rules reveal broader scaling principles. Visual documentation of the sustained collective rotation is available as Supplementary Video S1 [16].

To characterize the collective configurations of the system, we map continuous trajectories onto a coarse-grained spin representation. By projecting the instantaneous orientation of each agent onto the local tangent of the boundary, we assign binary states $s_l(t) = \pm 1$, which enable the definition of collective polarization and other statistical descriptors of the group state [17]. The underlying interaction structure is quantified through effective couplings $J_{l,n}$ [18] and individual directional biases via local fields h_l [19]. As illustrated in Fig. 1, these parameters reconstruct the relational architecture of coordination rules, effectively integrating diverse physical and sensory modalities into a unified stationary configurational structure.

Because the observed dynamics constitute a NESS with sustained probability currents, reciprocity of interactions cannot be assumed. This necessitates an explicitly asymmetric formulation of the effective coupling network [2, 20]. Building on spin-inspired active particle models [21], we develop an inference methodology that reconstructs effective interactions directly from trajectory data. We employ the inverse asymmetric Ising model (IAIM) [22–24] with two critical adaptations necessary for NESS inference: (i) pseudolikelihood maximization [25] to handle nonreciprocal interactions ($J_{l,n} \neq J_{n,l}$), and (ii) L_2 regularization to robustly distinguish genuine couplings from inference noise [24].

While the asymmetric Ising framework allows for nonreciprocal parameters, the quantified degree of nonreciprocity serves as an empirical signature of broken detailed balance within the coordination network [2, 26–28]. Whether nonreciprocal rules reflect inherent behavioral traits or emerge from collective responses to confinement remains a fundamental question. By focusing on minimal collectives, we aim to identify the interaction signatures that characterize the fundamental building blocks of collective behavior before they are obscured by large-scale averaging [29]. This approach, capturing behavior reminiscent of natural rock-pool environments [30–32], provides a framework to identify phenomena such as social screening, a group-size-mediated attenuation of interaction strength driven by the presence of intervening neighbors [33–35]. Analysis of the resulting coupling network links these observations to the principles of collective decision-making [36] and to synthetic nonreciprocal active systems [13, 20].

The paper proceeds as follows. Section II describes the mapping of trajectories onto a discrete spin representation and introduces the asymmetric Ising model as a description of the nonequilibrium steady state. Section III examines the variation of the inferred interaction

network with group size, identifying discriminative structural features via ensemble machine learning (Random Forest (RF) [37] and Gradient Boosting (GB) [38]) and nonparametric testing. Dimensionality reduction together with multinomial logistic regression (MLR) [39] is then used to characterize the geometric organization of the feature space and to determine the minimal two-feature models. Section IV interprets these results in terms of an orthogonality principle, linking interaction heterogeneity to statistical volatility and framing nonreciprocity as an emergent degree of freedom. Finally, Sec. V synthesizes the findings into a general framework for inferring

Figure 1: Mapping collective motion onto an asymmetric Ising model. (a) Confinement in a circular arena restricts shrimp trajectories to boundary following, reducing motion to a binary directional choice: clockwise (+1) or counterclockwise (−1). (b) Illustration of nonreciprocal coupling ($J_{12} \neq J_{21}$), a hallmark of active systems that breaks detailed balance. (c,d) Two limiting pair configurations: co-rotation ($s_1 = s_2$) and counter-rotation ($s_1 \neq s_2$). (e,f) Network representations of inferred effective couplings $J_{l,n}$ for groups of $N = 3$ (triangular) and $N = 4$ (square) individuals. Panels (a–f) collectively outline the conceptual transition from empirical trajectories to a coarse-grained spin description used throughout this work.

Figure 2: Overview of the video-processing pipeline. The tracking process starts with video recording of shrimp in a circular experimental arena (a). Panel (b) shows the result of object detection using the `idtracker.ai` tool, followed by ellipse fitting to binary contours of a single shrimp. Panel (c) illustrates the determination of orientation (\mathbf{n}) based on the major axis of the fitted ellipse and the detected head position.

nonequilibrium interactions in confined active collectives.

II. METHODS

A. Experimental Setup

Experiments were conducted in circular glass arenas, which confined shrimp trajectories to a defined boundary. Size-matched male shrimp were recorded for eight independent trials per group size ($N = 2, 3, 4$). Each trial was recorded for a duration sufficient to ensure robust statistical sampling of the nonequilibrium steady state. The recording frame rate was chosen to explicitly resolve the rapid directional switches critical for capturing instantaneous spin configurations and for inferring the underlying effective coupling network. Technical specifications supporting the experimental protocols are deferred to Appendix A.

B. Trajectory Analysis and Preprocessing

Trajectories of shrimp groups ($N = 2, 3, 4$) were extracted using the open-source AI-based tracking software `idtracker.ai` [40], selected for its robust group-size identity preservation in dense collectives [41]. An overview of the automated tracking pipeline is provided in Fig. 2. Head-orientation detection mapped the major axis of each individual to angles $\theta_l(t) \in [0, 360^\circ)$ directed toward the head [as illustrated in Fig. 2(b)].

The processed trajectories ($x_l(t), y_l(t), \theta_l(t)$) were exported as plain-text files for downstream statistical-mechanical analysis. Orientation angles $\theta_l(t)$ were mapped to unit vectors $\mathbf{n}_l(t)$ (Fig. 2(c)), and positions were referenced to the arena center to form coordinate pairs $(\mathbf{r}_{c,l}(t), \mathbf{n}_l(t))$ for each shrimp l , where $\|\mathbf{r}_{c,l}(t)\| = r_{c,l}(t)$ denotes the instantaneous distance from the arena center to the l -th shrimp.

Thigmotaxis drives positioning, quantified by the geometric mean radial distance:

$$r_{c,\text{geom}}(t) = \left(\prod_{l=1}^N r_{c,l}(t) \right)^{1/N}, \quad (1)$$

We utilize $r_{c,\text{geom}}(t)$ as the geometric group coordinate. This multiplicative definition provides the strictest measure of collective boundary adherence, as it is dominated by the most central individual. A single individual near the arena center ($r_{c,l}(t) \approx 0$) dominates the geometric mean, pulling it toward zero. The collective adherence is thus strictly quantified by the most central individual within the group. Higher $r_{c,\text{geom}}(t)$ levels provide a physically robust measure of the group's overall boundary adherence.

As an intermediate analytical step, we define a continuous spin coordinate by projecting each shrimp's orientation vector onto the local tangential direction:

$$s_l^{\text{cont}}(t) = \boldsymbol{\tau}_l(t) \cdot \mathbf{n}_l(t), \quad (2)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\tau}_l(t)$ denotes the unit tangent vector to the arena circumference at position $\mathbf{r}_{c,l}(t)$, orthogonal to the radial direction. This coordinate spans the interval $[-1, 1]$ and quantifies the degree of tangential alignment: positive values correspond to clockwise orientation, negative values to counterclockwise orientation. The quantity $s_l^{\text{cont}}(t)$ thus provides a one-dimensional collective variable that captures motion along the circular boundary. Projecting onto the tangential direction ensures a physically meaningful mapping that respects the continuous geometry of the arena while enabling systematic statistical analysis of orientation dynamics.

Empirical distributions of $s_l^{\text{cont}}(t)$ exhibit strong bimodality across all group sizes (Fig. 3), reflecting the confinement and thigmotaxis that restrict motion to clockwise and counter-clockwise directions. This pronounced directional bistability justifies the reduction to binary spins $s_l = \pm 1$, a standard coarse-graining widely used in studies of confined active matter with similar two-state dynamics [21–24]. Consequently, the binary approximation faithfully captures the dominant collective degree of freedom, allowing us to apply the asymmetric Ising framework for inferring the effective pairwise couplings $J_{l,n}$.

C. Asymmetric Ising Model

We model the effective interaction network using an asymmetric Ising model. The spin configuration $\mathbf{s}(t) = \{s_1(t), \dots, s_N(t)\}$ encodes the instantaneous tangential direction of each shrimp l ($s_l(t) = +1$ for clockwise, -1 for counterclockwise). The coupling matrix $\mathbf{J} = \{J_{l,n}\}$ is fully asymmetric ($J_{l,n} \neq J_{n,l}$), capturing stationary directional asymmetries in pairwise correlations, while external fields $\mathbf{h} = \{h_l\}$ represent individual directional preferences.

Figure 3: Empirical justification for spin discretization. The distribution of the continuous spin coordinate $s_l^{\text{cont}}(t)$ shows pronounced peaks at $+1$ (clockwise) and -1 (counterclockwise) across all radial distances and group sizes ($N = 2, 3, 4$). This persistent bimodality confirms that the dominant collective degree of freedom is a binary choice, warranting the Ising model perspective.

Parameters are inferred via the maximum entropy (MaxEnt) principle, yielding the least biased distribution consistent with observed single-spin averages $\langle s_l \rangle$ and pairwise correlations $\langle s_l s_n \rangle$. This parsimonious approach—suited to the system’s NESS characterized by low-count and intermittent observations—treats trajectory data as a collection of statistically independent, steady-state snapshots. In this framework, the inferred IAIM parameters represent a coarse-grained, stationary signature of the underlying nonequilibrium interaction topology.

In contrast to traditional equilibrium Ising models, which assume pairwise exchange symmetry ($J_{l,n} = J_{n,l}$), our approach utilizes the IAIM framework to explicitly handle nonreciprocal interactions ($J_{l,n} \neq J_{n,l}$), which are ubiquitous in active and biological systems [26–29]. The inferred asymmetry is used to characterize and quantify nonreciprocal behavior in confined shrimp collectives. To achieve this, we minimize a regularized log-pseudolikelihood function using an ensemble of subsampled observations, an approach known for its robust group-size identity preservation in dense interaction environ-

ments [17, 25].

This MaxEnt framework is implemented via pseudo-likelihood maximization as follows. The probability of an individual shrimp l changing its rotational state from s_l to $-s_l$, given the instantaneous configuration of all other spins \mathbf{s}_{-l} , is defined by the logistic function:

$$P(s_l \rightarrow -s_l | \mathbf{s}_{-l}) = \frac{1}{1 + \exp(2s_l h_{\text{eff},l})}, \quad (3)$$

where the effective local field acting on shrimp l is $h_{\text{eff},l} = \sum_{n \neq l} J_{l,n} s_n + h_l$. \mathbf{s}_{-l} denotes the configuration of all spins excluding s_l . The Inverse Ising Problem (or Maximum Likelihood Estimation) is then solved by iteratively determining the parameters $\{\mathbf{J}, \mathbf{h}\}$ that maximize the likelihood of observing the empirical spin configurations based on this defined transition rate. The inverse temperature is incorporated directly into the parameters $J_{l,n}$ and h_l for simplicity, ensuring their relative strengths and signs remain physically meaningful [42, 43].

The key distinction of the asymmetric approach is the explicit violation of detailed balance by the asymmetric coupling matrix \mathbf{J} . This effect—a necessary condition for the NESS of an active system—physically mandates the adoption of $J_{l,n} \neq J_{n,l}$. The resulting log-probability stationary structure thus serves as an effective cost function characterizing the NESS, in direct contrast to a conservative equilibrium potential.

1. Inference Pipeline

The detailed implementation of the iterative fitting procedure is summarized in the Algorithms Summary (see Appendix B).

Model parameters $\Theta^{(i,j)} = (\mathbf{J}^{(i,j)}, \mathbf{h}^{(i,j)})$ are inferred separately for each experimental trial i ($N_{\text{trial}} = 8$ per group size) and subsample j (N_{sub}). Subsampling is performed by selecting $T_{L_{\text{sub}}} = \lfloor \gamma_L T_L \rfloor$ time points with replacement, deliberately reshuffling temporal order to enforce a maximum-entropy steady-state description [44]. While this focus is on the stationary distribution, the use of an asymmetric matrix \mathbf{J} allows the model to capture local directional asymmetries and chiral correlations inherent in the steady-state snapshots. In this framework, the inferred nonreciprocity ($J_{l,n} \neq J_{n,l}$) acts as a stationary signature of the underlying nonequilibrium drive, mapping nonconservative features of the biological assembly onto the structural geometry. Importantly, because inference is performed on temporally decorrelated snapshots, this asymmetry reflects a structural property of the stationary distribution and does not constitute a direct demonstration of temporal causality or of specific directional behavioral mechanisms such as leader–follower dynamics. Ensemble averaging over independent subsamples, combined with L_2 regularization (λ_{L_2}), yields robust estimates of couplings \mathbf{J} and fields \mathbf{h} .

Inference follows the maximum-entropy principle [42, 45], selecting the pairwise asymmetric Ising model that

best reproduces observed single-spin polarizations and pairwise correlations while remaining parsimonious. The pseudolikelihood

$$L_{\text{PL}}(\Theta^{(i,j)}) = \prod_{k=1}^{T_{L\text{sub}}} \prod_{l=1}^N P(s_l^{(i,j)}(k) | \mathbf{s}_{-l}^{(i,j)}(k)) \quad (4)$$

approximates the joint probability by a product of conditionals, using the Boltzmann form consistent with Glauber dynamics (Eq. 3). This factorization enables tractable optimization in correlated systems while neglecting explicit temporal dependencies.

Parameters are obtained by minimizing the regularized negative log-pseudolikelihood

$$F(\Theta^{(i,j)}) = -\log L_{\text{PL}}(\Theta^{(i,j)}) + \frac{\lambda_{\text{L2}}}{2} \sum_{l,n=1}^N (J_{l,n}^{(i,j)})^2, \quad (5)$$

using the L-BFGS-B algorithm [46]. See Algorithm 1 for details.

The asymmetric couplings $J_{l,n} \neq J_{n,l}$ represent a stationary signature of the nonequilibrium drive, explicitly violating detailed balance. The log-probability distribution is interpreted as an effective cost function

$$\mathcal{H}_{\text{eff}}^{(i,j)}(k) = -\left(\mathbf{s}^{(i,j)}(k)^\top \mathbf{J}^{\text{sym},(i,j)} \mathbf{s}^{(i,j)}(k) + \mathbf{h}^{(i,j)\top} \mathbf{s}^{(i,j)}(k) \right), \quad (6)$$

Note that the effective cost function \mathcal{H}_{eff} represents the negative log-probability of the stationary state, conceptually bridging the empirical likelihood of the inverse mapping (Eq. 5) with the internal structural stability of the collective configuration modes. The term $\mathbf{J}^{\text{sym},(i,j)} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{J}^{(i,j)} + \mathbf{J}^{(i,j)\top})$ isolates the structural stiffness of the dominant configuration modes, while the antisymmetric part accounts for broken reciprocity and the twisted geometry of the nonequilibrium steady-state structure. Crucially, the parameters $\mathbf{J}^{(i,j)}$ and $\mathbf{h}^{(i,j)}$ remain fixed over the analyzed segment when computing the NESS fluctuation features (Eqs. (11), (14), (5)). These inferred parameters project the complexity of the collective state into a parsimonious pairwise framework, defining the interaction network driving group polarization. Algorithm parameters and mathematical notation are summarized in Table I and Table II, respectively.

2. Feature Definitions

To characterize the inferred effective coupling network, its relation to the NESS, and its spectral properties, we defined 13 features (\mathcal{X}_1 – \mathcal{X}_{13}) (Table III). These metrics quantify key architectural and statistical aspects of the coupling matrix \mathbf{J} , linking empirical group patterns to the network organization. The explicit calculation of these features from the inferred parameters $\Theta^{(i,j)}$ is detailed in Algorithm 2 (Appendix).

Parameter	Symbol	Value (Description)
Number of trials	N_{trial}	8 (replicates)
Unified length	$T_{L\text{uni}}$	36 000 frames
Total volume	—	288 000 snapshots
Group size	N	2, 3, 4
Subsamples	N_{sub}	200, 5000 (ensemble)
Fraction	γ_L	0.5, 1.0
Sample length	$T_{L\text{sub}}$	$\lfloor \gamma_L T_{L\text{uni}} \rfloor$
Regularization	λ_{L2}	10^{-3} (Ridge)
Tolerance	tol	10^{-6} (L-BFGS-B)

Table I: Computational and algorithm parameters for the inverse Ising inference. Reconstructed from a total volume of 288 000 snapshots per group size, the pipeline was implemented in Python 3.9 using SciPy (L-BFGS-B), NumPy, and Joblib for parallelization. This extensive sampling ensures that inferred couplings \mathbf{J} and fields \mathbf{h} are robustly determined, with stability validated across multiple ensemble sizes (N_{sub}) and data fractions (γ_L).

Symbol	Definition
$\Theta^{(i,j)}$	Parameters for trial i , subsample j : $(\mathbf{J}^{(i,j)}, \mathbf{h}^{(i,j)})$.
$s_l^{(i,j)}(k)$	Spin of shrimp l : $\{-1, +1\}$; at observation k .
$J_{l,n}^{(i,j)}$	Coupling magnitude; influence of shrimp n on l .
$h_l^{(i,j)}$	External field l ; boundary-driven thigmotactic bias.
$\mathbf{s}^{(i,j)}(k)$	Full spin configuration at observation index k .
$\mathbf{s}_{-l}^{(i,j)}(k)$	Configuration vector excluding the l -th spin.
$\mathbf{J}^{\text{sym}}, \mathbf{J}^{\text{asym}}$	Symmetric and antisymmetric coupling parts.
$\lambda_\nu^{(i,j)}$	ν -th eigenvalue of the effective coupling matrix \mathbf{J} .
$\mathcal{X}_m^{(i,j)}$	Extracted network, NESS, or algebraic-spectral feature m (1–13).
$\mathcal{H}_{\text{eff}}^{(i,j)}(k)$	Effective cost function value at observation k .
$\overline{\mathcal{H}_{\text{eff}}^{(i,j)}}$	Average effective cost function value over the sample segment.
$r_{c,i,l}(t)$	Radial distance of shrimp l in trial i at time t .
$r_{c,\text{geom}}(t)$	Geometric mean radial distance of the group at time t .
$\mathbf{n}_l, \boldsymbol{\tau}_l$	Head-orientation vector and unit tangent to the boundary.
$s_l^{\text{cont}}(t)$	Continuous spin projection: alignment with the tangent $(\boldsymbol{\tau}_l \cdot \mathbf{n}_l)$.
$\mathbb{I}(\cdot)$	Indicator function (1 if condition is true, 0 otherwise).

Table II: Mathematical notation and definitions. The table summarizes symbols used for trajectory analysis, asymmetric Ising inference, and feature extraction. Indices (i, j) refer to trials and bootstrap realizations; k and t denote sampling and frame indices, respectively.

Table III: Feature Summary and Interpretation. Features 1–4 quantify interaction scale, 5–8 describe the fluctuation properties of the NESS, and 9–13 characterize the algebraic and spectral geometry of the effective coupling matrix (\mathcal{X}_{13} is included for completeness of the spectral characterization, but due to the high sparsity of complex eigenvalues in the studied ensembles, it is omitted from subsequent statistical analysis). Standardized units allow for direct comparison of feature magnitudes across different physical dimensions.

Category	Feature	Symbol	Physical Interpretation
Interaction	1	\mathcal{X}_1	Mean coupling strength; coordination magnitude.
	2	\mathcal{X}_2	Interaction heterogeneity; structural variance.
	3	\mathcal{X}_3	Fraction of negative couplings; frustration.
	4	\mathcal{X}_4	Average external field; thigmotactic bias.
NESS	5	\mathcal{X}_5	NESS stability measure; structural consistency.
	6	\mathcal{X}_6	Mean spin polarization; collective orientation.
	7	\mathcal{X}_7	Statistical volatility ($\sim \text{PC}_1$); state-space fluctuation.
	8	\mathcal{X}_8	Interaction consistency; fraction of satisfied terms.
Algebraic & Spectral	9	\mathcal{X}_9	Spectral radius (real part); mode amplification.
	10	\mathcal{X}_{10}	Minimum spectral gap; mode separation.
	11	\mathcal{X}_{11}	Mean spectral gap; relaxation structure.
	12	\mathcal{X}_{12}	Nonreciprocal asymmetry; network directedness.
	13	\mathcal{X}_{13}	Fraction of complex eigenvalues; complex modes.

a. Interaction-Level Features (\mathcal{X}_1 – \mathcal{X}_4) The following features quantify the inferred interaction structure and collectively characterize pairwise coordination:

$$\mathcal{X}_1^{(i,j)} = \frac{1}{N(N-1)} \sum_{\substack{l,n=1 \\ l \neq n}}^N |J_{l,n}^{(i,j)}|, \quad (7)$$

$$\mathcal{X}_2^{(i,j)} = \sqrt{\frac{1}{N(N-1)} \sum_{l \neq n}^N (|J_{l,n}^{(i,j)}| - \mathcal{X}_1^{(i,j)})^2}, \quad (8)$$

$$\mathcal{X}_3^{(i,j)} = \frac{1}{N(N-1)} \sum_{\substack{l,n=1 \\ l \neq n}}^N \mathbb{I}(J_{l,n}^{(i,j)} < 0), \quad (9)$$

$$\mathcal{X}_4^{(i,j)} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{l=1}^N |h_l^{(i,j)}|. \quad (10)$$

Here, \mathcal{X}_1 represents the mean coupling strength, reflecting coordination intensity; \mathcal{X}_2 captures coupling heterogeneity, indicating variability in absolute interaction strengths; \mathcal{X}_3 quantifies antagonistic interactions through negative couplings; and \mathcal{X}_4 determines the boundary-induced bias, serving as a statistical proxy for the strength of the thigmotactic drive.

b. NESS Features (\mathcal{X}_5 – \mathcal{X}_8) To capture temporal fluctuations in collective dynamics, we compute the following features over $T_{L\text{sub}}$ subsampled data segments (snapshot ensembles) from each trial trajectory. These metrics integrate the inferred coupling structure with spin dynamics, providing a comprehensive view of NESS behavior:

$$\mathcal{X}_5^{(i,j)} = \frac{1}{NT_{L\text{sub}}} \sum_{k=1}^{T_{L\text{sub}}} \mathcal{H}_{\text{eff}}^{(i,j)}(k) = \overline{\mathcal{H}_{\text{eff}}^{(i,j)}}, \quad (11)$$

$$\mathcal{X}_6^{(i,j)} = \frac{1}{NT_{L\text{sub}}} \sum_{k=1}^{T_{L\text{sub}}} \sum_{l=1}^N s_l^{(i,j)}(k), \quad (12)$$

$$\mathcal{X}_7^{(i,j)} = \frac{1}{NT_{L\text{sub}}} \sum_{k=1}^{T_{L\text{sub}}} (\mathcal{H}_{\text{eff}}^{(i,j)}(k) - \overline{\mathcal{H}_{\text{eff}}^{(i,j)}})^2, \quad (13)$$

$$\mathcal{X}_8^{(i,j)} = \frac{1}{N(N-1)T_{L\text{sub}}} \sum_{k=1}^{T_{L\text{sub}}} S^{(i,j)}(k), \quad (14)$$

where

$$S^{(i,j)}(k) = \sum_{\substack{l,n=1 \\ l \neq n}}^N \mathbb{I}(J_{l,n}^{(i,j)} s_l^{(i,j)}(k) s_n^{(i,j)}(k) > 0).$$

Here, \mathcal{X}_5 quantifies the NESS stability measure, characterizing the average statistical weight of the observed configurations within the stationary probability distribution. \mathcal{X}_6 quantifies the mean spin polarization, \mathcal{X}_7 the statistical volatility, and \mathcal{X}_8 the average fraction of satisfied interactions. The effective cost function $\mathcal{H}_{\text{eff}}^{(i,j)}(k)$ is defined in Eq. (6). It is important to note that coupling matrix $\mathbf{J}^{(i,j)}$ is inferred from the entire segment and remains fixed during the evaluation of $S^{(i,j)}(k)$. Consequently, \mathcal{X}_8 which utilizes the indicator function $\mathbb{I}(\dots)$ quantifies the degree to which the observed spin dynamics align with the segment-specific interaction regime. This provides a direct probe of behavioral consistency under the inferred coupling network.

c. Algebraic and Spectral Features (\mathcal{X}_9 , \mathcal{X}_{10} , \mathcal{X}_{11} , \mathcal{X}_{12} , \mathcal{X}_{13}) The spectral properties of the inferred effective coupling matrix \mathbf{J} characterize the structural organization of the collective state by defining the geometric features of the underlying probability stationary structure. Within the asymmetric Ising framework, \mathbf{J} encodes the stationary statistical couplings that shape the steady-state distri-

bution, where a linear analysis of fluctuations reveals how the eigenvalues govern the local structural stiffness. Specifically, the real parts of these eigenvalues quantify the statistical stiffness along the corresponding eigenvectors; larger positive values indicate directions of statistical reinforcement associated with higher-weight configuration modes, whereas lower values signal a stationary structure flattening and a corresponding increase in susceptibility to fluctuations. The presence of nonreciprocal coupling structures is further manifested through complex conjugate pairs of eigenvalues λ_ν , which signify a twisted, nonequilibrium steady-state geometry—a statistical remnant of the cyclic behavior inherent in the original dynamical system. The dominant eigenvalue λ_{\max} sets the Overall scale of statistical sensitivity, while the spectral spacing characterizes the separation between primary collective modes. Crucially, as \mathbf{J} is inferred from temporally decorrelated snapshots, the eigenvalues λ_ν represent collective directions in state space along which the probability distribution is most sensitive to perturbations, rather than temporal decay rates. This procedure extracts the robust, time-invariant relational structure embedded in the coupling network. The algebraic and spectral features are defined as follows. The spectral radius

$$\mathcal{X}_9^{(i,j)} = \max_\nu |\operatorname{Re}(\lambda_\nu^{(i,j)})|, \quad (15)$$

where $\lambda_\nu^{(i,j)}$ are the eigenvalues of the coupling matrix $\mathbf{J}^{(i,j)}$. Here and throughout Eqs. (15)–(16), the absolute value denotes the absolute real part: $|\lambda_\nu| \equiv |\operatorname{Re}(\lambda_\nu)|$. This quantity measures the magnitude of the dominant relaxation-like mode, interpreted here as the principal stiffness direction of the inferred statistical stationary structure. The spectral gap \mathcal{X}_{10} measures the separation between the dominant mode and its nearest statistical neighbor:

$$\mathcal{X}_{10}^{(i,j)} = \min_{\nu \neq \nu^*} |\operatorname{Re}(\lambda_{\nu^*}^{(i,j)}) - \operatorname{Re}(\lambda_\nu^{(i,j)})|, \quad (16)$$

where $\nu^* = \arg \max_\nu \operatorname{Re}(\lambda_\nu^{(i,j)})$. This gap quantifies the isolation of the primary stiffness direction. The mean spectral gap is defined as

$$\mathcal{X}_{11}^{(i,j)} = \frac{\max_\nu \operatorname{Re}(\lambda_\nu^{(i,j)}) - \min_\nu \operatorname{Re}(\lambda_\nu^{(i,j)})}{N-1}, \quad (17)$$

representing the average spacing between the extremal real eigenvalues, which characterizes the overall density of modes in the stiffness spectrum.

The strength of nonreciprocal interactions is captured by:

$$\mathcal{X}_{12}^{(i,j)} = \frac{2}{N(N-1)} \sum_{1 \leq l < n \leq N} |J_{l,n}^{\text{asym},(i,j)}|, \quad (18)$$

where $\mathbf{J}^{\text{asym},(i,j)} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{J}^{(i,j)} - \mathbf{J}^{(i,j)\top})$ is the antisymmetric part of the coupling matrix. This quantity represents the average magnitude of directed interactions and serves as

a primary marker for the departure from detailed balance. Finally, the fraction of complex eigenvalues is defined as:

$$\mathcal{X}_{13}^{(i,j)} = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{\nu=1}^N \mathbb{I}(\operatorname{Im}(\lambda_\nu^{(i,j)}) \neq 0), \quad (19)$$

which identifies the emergence of non-Hermitian spectral features. In the underlying dynamical system, such modes would signal potential oscillatory behavior, whereas here they quantify the degree to which the statistical stationary distribution deviates from a purely gradient-based geometry.

III. RESULTS

The selected feature set derived from the inferred interaction matrices includes twelve core physical metrics (\mathcal{X}_1 to \mathcal{X}_{12}), summarized in Table III. These quantify interaction topology, the statistical state of the stationary structure, and structural robustness. A thirteenth feature, the fraction of complex eigenvalues (\mathcal{X}_{13}), exhibited zero mean value and lacked variance across all group sizes, making it unsuitable for multivariate analysis; it is therefore excluded from the results. The integrated multi-modal analysis—bridging trajectory data, statistical feature extraction, and architectural classification—is summarized in the methodological framework (Fig. 4).

A. Group-size Scaling and Interaction Architecture

The progression of group size N reshapes the underlying interaction architecture through a sequence of distinct statistical features (Fig. 5). We identify three primary modes of response as the assembly grows.

First, a monotonic attenuation of the mean coupling strength \mathcal{X}_1 and the mean spectral gap \mathcal{X}_{11} suggests an effective *social screening* of pairwise interactions. Individual coordination effort is redistributed across an increasing number of neighbors, consistent with density-mediated effects in confined active matter.

Second, the transition from pairs to larger groups is marked by qualitative structural shifts. Interaction heterogeneity \mathcal{X}_2 rises sharply at $N = 3$ and saturates, as confirmed by global nonparametric testing and subsequent post-hoc comparisons (Kruskal-Wallis H-test followed by Dunn’s analysis yielding $p \approx 10^{-74}$ for the $N = 3 \rightarrow 4$; see Appendix C, Tables IV and V).

Concurrently, nonreciprocal asymmetry \mathcal{X}_{12} rises by more than two orders of magnitude (from $\sim 10^{-5}$ to $\sim 10^{-3}$), underscoring the emergence of strongly directed interactions as a defining structural feature of denser collectives. Boundary-induced biases (external field \mathcal{X}_4) exhibit nonmonotonic behavior ($0.414 \rightarrow 0.281 \rightarrow 0.293$), reflecting the interplay between innate thigmotaxis and emergent social coupling.

Third, the fraction of negative couplings (\mathcal{X}_3) reveals a transition through structural frustration. While pairs exhibit a median of zero negative couplings, triplets ($N = 3$) show a consistent emergence of negative terms ($\approx 33\%$, see Appendix C). To confirm that the transition to a robust nonreciprocal regime at $N = 4$ represents a genuine physical effect rather than a finite-sample artifact, we performed a parametric bootstrap null-model test (Appendix D, Table VI). This demonstrates that asymmetry at $N = 2$ and $N = 3$ is statistically indistinguishable from sampling noise, whereas the signal at $N = 4$ is highly significant, with a mean Z -score exceeding 40.

This reveals a clear hierarchical progression in the effective coupling network. While interaction heterogeneity (\mathcal{X}_2) establishes the group’s structural backbone already at $N = 3$, the transition to $N = 4$ is primarily driven by the emergence of robust nonreciprocal asymmetry (\mathcal{X}_{12}). This progression from simple coordination to heterogeneous and then directed interactions suggests a fundamental re-organization of the steady-state architecture as density increases.

B. NESS Fluctuations and Spectral Properties

Statistical volatility \mathcal{X}_7 increases monotonically with group size, indicating a progressive broadening of the effective cost function stationary structure. Although the NESS stability measure per spin (\mathcal{X}_5) becomes slightly less negative and the mean polarization (\mathcal{X}_6) shows no systematic trend, the fraction of satisfied pairwise interactions remains high ($\mathcal{X}_8 \gtrsim 0.61$). This confirms that the inferred symmetric couplings \mathbf{J}^{sym} reliably capture the dominant coordination forces even as volatility rises.

The spectral radius \mathcal{X}_9 and mean spectral gap \mathcal{X}_{11} characterize the global organization of the statistical structure. As group size increases, the network exerts a stronger statistical bias on rotational order (rising \mathcal{X}_9) while simultaneously lowering barriers between configurations (shrinking \mathcal{X}_{11} , Eq. 17). This spectral “crowding” reflects the reduction in statistical barriers between dominant collective modes, resulting in a broader repertoire of accessible states despite high global stiffness.

C. Identification of Structural Predictors (RF/GB and Kruskal-Wallis)

While the monotonic trends in global volatility and spectral density provide a clear signature of the system’s expansion (Section II), it remains an open question whether these broad statistical shifts encode a rigorous group-size identity. To isolate the unique architectural markers from this continuous statistical scaling, we applied ensemble machine learning models (RF and GB) on the globally standardized features \mathcal{X}_1 – \mathcal{X}_{12} . Both classifiers achieved a classification accuracy of 1.00, demonstrating complete separability of the three group sizes

Figure 4: Methodological Workflow and Physical Synthesis. The analytical pipeline transitions from behavioral mapping to structural interpretation across three distinct stages. (A) **Inverse Statistical Inference:** Effective interaction networks are established via L_2 -regularized pseudolikelihood maximization, yielding the asymmetric coupling matrix \mathbf{J} . (B) **Multi-Modal Analysis:** Interaction features are subjected to statistical ranking and dimensionality reduction, revealing that the primary group-size predictor, nonreciprocal asymmetry ($\mathcal{X}_{12} \uparrow$, i.e., increasing with N), resides on a structural identity subspace (PC₂) orthogonal to global statistical volatility (PC₁). (C) **Physical Synthesis:** The $N = 4$ architectural crossover is characterized by the internalization of constraints—a transition from boundary-driven dynamical flows to an internal network-driven steady-state structure—stabilized by spectral radius compression ($\mathcal{X}_{11} \downarrow$, i.e., decreasing with N).

Figure 5: Statistical aggregation of twelve features (\mathcal{X}_1 – \mathcal{X}_{12}) for $N = 2, 3, 4$. The markers represent ensemble-level statistics derived from individual trial means. The green solid line (median), blue dashed line (mean), and red dotted line (20% trimmed mean) illustrate the distribution of these trial-averaged values across 8 independent replicates. While features like \mathcal{X}_1 and \mathcal{X}_{11} show uniform scaling, others including \mathcal{X}_3 , \mathcal{X}_4 , and \mathcal{X}_5 exhibit a measured divergence between median and mean estimates. Such separation suggests underlying non-Gaussian distributions and localized structural shifts, most notably in the order-of-magnitude change of asymmetry (\mathcal{X}_{12}). These persistent scaling signatures indicate that specific features capture distinct aspects of the system’s growth, providing a basis for further structural analysis.

($N = 2, N = 3, N = 4$) on the training data.

Feature importance analysis (see Fig. 6 and Table VII in Appendix E) reveals a consistent hierarchy: interaction heterogeneity \mathcal{X}_2 and the nonreciprocity measure \mathcal{X}_{12} together account for approximately 76% of the total weight of the GB. This elite pair maintains high discriminative sensitivity across the entire $N = 2, 3, 4$ range (leading H -statistics, see Table IV). However, they exhibit distinct scaling roles: while \mathcal{X}_2 captures initial architectural shifts that begin to stabilize at $N = 4$ ($p \approx 10^{-74}$), structural directionality (\mathcal{X}_{12}) continues to emerge as a primary

Figure 6: Feature importance for RF and GB models on a logarithmic scale. Both approaches indicate the persistent dominance of \mathcal{X}_2 and \mathcal{X}_{12} .

discriminator as the collective expands. Consistent with our previous observation of scaling saturation, this divergence confirms that global heterogeneity establishes the group’s backbone early, whereas directionality provides the essential structural release for larger assemblies.

D. Structural Orthogonality and Profile Dissimilarity (PCA/UPGMA)

The separability demonstrated by the ensemble models (RF and GB) justifies the necessity of dimensionality reduction to uncover the underlying geometric structure of the feature space.

We perform a PCA to characterize the global variance of the feature space and to determine whether the most predictive structural features form a statistically independent axis. As shown in Fig. 7 and detailed in the loadings listed in Table VIII (Appendix E), the two primary predictors—interaction heterogeneity \mathcal{X}_2 and non-reciprocal asymmetry \mathcal{X}_{12} —project almost exclusively onto the second principal axis (PC_2). Conversely, the leading component PC_1 captures the correlated variation among interaction magnitudes and spectral properties, effectively representing an axis of statistical scale and volatility. This axis is defined by a cluster of features reflecting a continuum of coupling magnitude and distributional depth, evidenced by the large positive loadings of mean coupling \mathcal{X}_1 and statistical volatility \mathcal{X}_7 . Within this stationary probability distribution, these features are counterbalanced by the NESS stability measure \mathcal{X}_5 , which represents the average statistical alignment of the state. This organization reveals a fundamental architectural decoupling: while PC_1 governs the global statistical amplitude of the system, the group-size identity resides on a statistically independent, orthogonal subspace defined by PC_2 . Strikingly, the descriptors governing this second component exactly mirror the primary predictive triad (\mathcal{X}_2 , \mathcal{X}_{12} , \mathcal{X}_3) identified by the supervised ensemble classifiers (Table VII), confirming that the system’s intrinsic nonreciprocity is orthogonally encoded within

Figure 7: Collective states correspond to $N = 2$ (blue circles), $N = 3$ (orange squares), and $N = 4$ (green triangles). (a) PCA (46.0%+18.1% of total variance) reveals a progressive separation of group sizes along PC_2 , while PC_1 captures correlated variation across interaction magnitude, spectral properties, and statistical fluctuations. As demonstrated in (b,c), the utilization of UMAP and t-SNE projections substantiates the existence of a nonlinear structural element concomitant with group size. The presence of small clusters defined as eight trials per N serves as an indication of variability among trials.

the collective’s structural dispersion. The statistical independence of these components suggests that the group’s structural identity is not a trivial consequence of interaction strength. Instead, the identity and the overall scale of coordination represent decoupled physical mechanisms.

To complement the analysis, we performed hierarchical clustering of the feature set using the Unweighted Pair Group Method with Arithmetic Mean (UPGMA) based on Euclidean distance. The UPGMA dendrogram (see Fig. 8 and Appendix F) confirms this dissimilarity. The structural group size identity features (\mathcal{X}_2 and \mathcal{X}_{12}) remain distinct and do not form clusters at low Euclidean distances. This reinforces their statistical independence from the general magnitude features. The numerical linkage values are provided in Table IX.

The application of nonlinear techniques, specifically UMAP and t-SNE [Figs. 7(b) and 7(c)] [47], complements the PCA by validating its core structural findings. While PCA provides the maximum variance projection—exposing the global $N = 2 \leftrightarrow N = 3 \leftrightarrow N = 4$ gradient along PC_2 —the nonlinear embeddings were essential for dissecting the internal feature space geometry. Analysis of density plots [Figs. 7(a)–7(c)] supports the interpretation that the feature space is not uniformly dense. Nonlinear methods (UMAP, t-SNE) consistently expose internal sub-clustering. The ability to organize data into compact trial-manifolds demonstrates the robustness of these low-dimensional embeddings. To ensure that the observed nonreciprocal signature (\mathcal{X}_{12}) is of biological origin and not a sampling artifact, we validated its significance against a symmetric MaxEnt null-model ensemble; the resulting Z -scores confirm a robust departure from equilibrium at $N = 4$ (see Table VI and Appendix D).

The statistical separation of features proves that the structural properties, notably interaction heterogeneity (\mathcal{X}_2) and nonreciprocal asymmetry (\mathcal{X}_{12}), are the primary factors contributing to PC_2 , the axis orthogonal to PC_1 . This fundamental dissociation—where network-derived structural variables (including the boundary-driven thigmotaxis quantified by \mathcal{X}_4) are statistically distinct from the general magnitude axis—validates our feature engineering approach. The alignment of \mathcal{X}_4 with the other identity-defining features on PC_2 confirms that confinement-induced boundary influence is an integral part of the collective’s structural backbone. However, while dimensionality reduction and nonlinear clustering methods visually support this organization, they are descriptive and cannot fully quantify the optimal linear separation boundary. Therefore, a multiclass classification via MLR is required to precisely weight the specific contributions of these structural features to the system’s log-odds distribution. The numerical results for model validation and significance are explicitly listed in the Appendix C.

E. Group-Size Classification via Multinomial Logistic Regression

Multinomial logistic regression (MLR) analyses were performed on globally standardized features (Z-scores), including a combinatorial search over all possible one- and two-feature models. We adopt $N = 4$ as the reference class. Each realization is represented by the input vector $\mathbf{X} = [1, \mathcal{X}_1, \dots, \mathcal{X}_{n_p}]^\top$, where the first entry accounts for the intercept. The conditional probability π_z of observing a collective of size $N = z$ is determined by the log-odds relationship with respect to the reference class:

$$\ln\left(\frac{\pi_z}{\pi_{N=4}}\right) = \boldsymbol{\gamma}_z^\top \mathbf{X}, \quad (20)$$

where $\boldsymbol{\gamma}_z = [\gamma_{z,0}, \gamma_{z,1}, \dots, \gamma_{z,n_p}]^\top$ is the coefficient vector for class $z \in \{2, 3\}$. The complete model for the two non-reference classes is thus specified by a $2 \times (n_p + 1)$ coefficient matrix of log-odds contrasts. Detailed combinatorial results and feature rankings are provided in Appendix G.

1. Single-Feature Regression: The \mathcal{X}_2 Scaling Axis

The single-feature regression ($n_p = 1$) establishes a linear benchmark for group-size discrimination. The feature \mathcal{X}_2 (interaction heterogeneity) emerges as the most parsimonious single predictor, recording the minimal BIC (Table X in Appendix G). However, its modest accuracy (≈ 0.59) is insufficient for robust classification across all group sizes, mandating the transition to two-feature models. On the standardized scale (Z-scores), the coefficient matrix for the log-odds contrasts relative to the $N = 4$ reference class is:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \gamma_{2,0} & \gamma_{2,2} \\ \gamma_{3,0} & \gamma_{3,2} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 0.462 & -26.366 \\ 0.487 & -26.299 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (21)$$

The large magnitude and consistently negative signs of the \mathcal{X}_2 coefficients identify it as a primary determinant of structural complexity. In this linear representation, increasing interaction heterogeneity acts as a sharp suppression mechanism for the log-odds of the $N = 2$ and $N = 3$ identities. This result statistically characterizes the $N = 4$ collective as a state defined by a significantly higher degree of interaction variability, which effectively separates it from the more homogeneous configurations of smaller groups. The prominence of this nonreciprocal feature suggests that collective identity is primarily defined by its departure from detailed balance. This property reflects the directed sensing required for boundary navigation, effectively mapping the 'invisible wall' effect onto the log-odds distribution.

2. Two-Feature Models: Structural and Spectral Discriminators

To determine how these structural features interact and whether their combination further enhances discriminability, we extend our analysis to two-feature models. The transition to two-feature models sharply reduces the Bayesian Information Criterion (BIC) compared to the single-feature benchmark. Our combinatorial scan of all possible feature pairs (Table XI) reveals a clear trade-off between statistical parsimony and predictive accuracy. Among all combinations, the model based on the system's structural architecture emerges as the superior classifier.

a. Best Structural Model ($\mathcal{X}_2 + \mathcal{X}_{12}$): The combination of interaction heterogeneity (\mathcal{X}_2) and nonreciprocal asymmetry (\mathcal{X}_{12}) provides the most robust identification of group size. This pairing achieves robust fidelity (Acc. ≈ 0.99) with the overall minimal BIC.

The standardized coefficient matrix relative to the $N = 4$ reference class is:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \gamma_{2,0} & \gamma_{2,2} & \gamma_{2,12} \\ \gamma_{3,0} & \gamma_{3,2} & \gamma_{3,12} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} -6.010 & -18.731 & -19.051 \\ -0.563 & 2.695 & -29.130 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (22)$$

The nonreciprocal asymmetry (\mathcal{X}_{12}) acts as the defining boundary marker. The exceptionally large negative coefficient for \mathcal{X}_{12} in the $N = 3$ contrast ($\gamma_{3,12} = -29.13$) confirms that the emergence of directed interactions is the critical structural hallmark of the $N = 4$ collective state.

b. Minimal Spectral Model ($\mathcal{X}_9 + \mathcal{X}_{11}$): An alternative pairing of spectral features also yields robust classification (Acc. ≈ 0.92). This model characterizes the group-size identity through the organization of the inferred statistical architecture.

The standardized coefficient matrix is:

$$\begin{pmatrix} \gamma_{2,0} & \gamma_{2,9} & \gamma_{2,11} \\ \gamma_{3,0} & \gamma_{3,9} & \gamma_{3,11} \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 4.097 & -20.741 & 24.953 \\ 7.051 & -11.884 & 14.783 \end{pmatrix}. \quad (23)$$

The large positive coefficients for the spectral gap \mathcal{X}_{11} (e.g., 24.953 for $N = 2$) quantify the significant spectral compression observed as group size increases. This spectral "crowding" reflects the reduction in statistical barriers between dominant collective modes in larger assemblies.

IV. DISCUSSION

The emergence of collective order from individual stochasticity is often framed through the lens of alignment and density-driven transitions occurring in the large- N limit. Our results suggest that even in minimal collectives, group-size identity is encoded in a topological reconfiguration of the interaction architecture.

The Kruskal–Wallis and post-hoc Dunn's tests confirm highly significant separation of group sizes across all architectural features (Appendix C). To ensure that the observed attenuation of mean coupling strength (\mathcal{X}_1),

the rise of interaction heterogeneity (\mathcal{X}_2), and spectral compression (\mathcal{X}_9 – \mathcal{X}_{11}) are not trivial artifacts of changing matrix dimensionality, we use the nonreciprocal asymmetry (\mathcal{X}_{12}) as a critical internal control. Our parametric bootstrap analysis (Appendix D) demonstrates that while this most delicate observable remains indistinguishable from sampling noise at $N = 2$ and $N = 3$, it emerges as a statistically robust signal only at $N = 4$. The fact that the identical inference pipeline does not generate spurious asymmetry at lower N strongly supports that the transitions observed at $N = 4$ reflect a genuine architectural shift in confined active matter rather than numerical byproducts.

A. The Orthogonality Principle: Decoupling Structure from Statistical Volatility

A central outcome of this study is the statistical separation between group-size identity and global correlated variation. This finding, evidenced by the orthogonality of principal components (Appendix E) and hierarchical clustering (Appendix F), reveals a fundamental architectural decoupling: structural features like heterogeneity (\mathcal{X}_2) and asymmetry (\mathcal{X}_{12}) are statistically independent from the primary variance axis (PC_1).

As shown in Fig. 7, PC_1 represents a composite statistical mode (46.0% of total variance) linking the mean coupling magnitude (\mathcal{X}_1) to the amplitude of fluctuations. Our eigenvector analysis (Appendix E) confirms that PC_1 is primarily defined by the typical interaction scale, acting as an indicator of statistical volatility within the stationary probability distribution. In contrast, group-size identity resides on a statistically independent subspace (PC_2 , 18.1%), confirming that the factors determining the magnitude of collective interactions are distinct from those encoding the underlying network architecture.

B. From Boundary-Driven to Network-Dominated Dynamics

The external bias (\mathcal{X}_4) represents the noninteracting contribution to the system's stationary architecture. Analogous to an external magnetic field in an Ising-like model, it imposes a uniform symmetry-breaking preference that drives states independently of mutual couplings. Biologically, this captures the thigmotactic drive—a baseline spatial constraint reflecting the innate tendency of individuals to remain near boundaries. In statistical terms, \mathcal{X}_4 shifts probability weights within the configurational space without altering the discrete nature of the states.

Our analysis reveals that as N increases, the statistical weight shifts from this geometry-induced bias toward emergent social features, \mathcal{X}_2 and \mathcal{X}_{12} . This characterizes a qualitative crossover from a geometry-dominated regime at $N = 2$ to a network-dominated regime at $N = 4$. The observed drop in \mathcal{X}_4 (Fig. 5) indicates that as the group

grows, individual thigmotactic preference is superseded by sociotaxis as the primary steering force. This suggests that $N = 4$ is the minimal configuration capable of generating sufficient internal structural pressure to balance environmental constraints, effectively internalizing the boundary geometry into a self-organized network regime.

Biologically, this crossover highlights the onset of collective sensing. The reduction of \mathcal{X}_4 and the concomitant emergence of nonreciprocal asymmetry (\mathcal{X}_{12}) suggest that for $N \geq 3$, the social interaction network itself begins to function as an internal "invisible wall". The directed character of these couplings ($J_{l,n} \neq J_{n,l}$) is consistent with an asymmetric influence structure, although the current framework does not resolve its mechanistic basis. In thermodynamic terms, this mirrors a state-space reconfiguration where internal exchange couplings overcome the symmetry-breaking external bias, allowing the steady-state to dynamically minimize environmental vulnerability.

C. Architectural Mechanisms: From Frustration to Nonreciprocity

The transition from pairs to larger groups is governed by a redistribution of coordination authority. A qualitative shift occurs at $N = 3$, marked by a pronounced rise in heterogeneity (\mathcal{X}_2 , $p < 10^{-100}$) and the emergence of antagonistic couplings (\mathcal{X}_3). This identifies $N = 3$ as a regime of structural frustration, where optimal pairwise arrangements for all nodes cannot be simultaneously satisfied.

As the system scales to $N = 4$, it resolves these static configurational conflicts by pivoting toward nonreciprocity (\mathcal{X}_{12}). The robust emergence of asymmetry at $N = 4$ ($Z > 40$), coinciding with the resolution of the $N = 3$ frustration peak (\mathcal{X}_3), confirms that the collective transcends static conflicts in favor of a nonconservative NESS. This suggests that the social interaction network is no longer purely reactive to individual noise; instead, the directed interaction asymmetry acts as a stabilizing mechanism, providing the group with a coherent collective identity and increased identifiability in the interaction space.

D. Spectral Consequences and Distributional Flattening

The spectral features (\mathcal{X}_9 , \mathcal{X}_{11}) characterize the global organization of the stationary distribution. As group size increases, the network evolves under a dynamical trade-off: it exerts a stronger statistical bias toward rotational order (rising \mathcal{X}_9) while simultaneously lowering barriers to alternative configurations (shrinking \mathcal{X}_{11}). This spectral compression signifies a narrowing of the spectral gap, indicating that larger collectives operate in a regime of increased dynamical flexibility.

The reduction in \mathcal{X}_{11} implies a systematic flattening of

the stationary probability distribution. Consequently, the $N = 4$ collective occupies a state where a broader repertoire of configurations is accessible despite high global stiffness. This ensures that group-size identity is robustly partitioned between the average interaction scale and the internal architectural dispersion.

E. Implications and Outlook

Our framework identifies interaction heterogeneity (\mathcal{X}_2) and nonreciprocal asymmetry (\mathcal{X}_{12}) as the primary predictors of group size, while confirming that collective behavior is robustly partitioned into two orthogonal components. This orthogonality principle suggests that heterogeneity and nonreciprocity are generic features of collective states in active matter. Capturing these rules is essential for moving beyond idealized representations toward realistic minimal models.

The data-driven pipeline presented here provides a scalable template for uncovering hidden structural rules in other nonequilibrium systems, from robotic swarms to biological tissues. By distilling high-dimensional dynamics into these fundamental axes, we establish a robust framework for predicting emergent behavior across diverse physical scales.

Future efforts using agent-based modeling could translate these inferred weights into dynamic rules. By defining agents with competing thigmotactic and sociotactic responses, one could explicitly test the universality of the decoupling between interaction magnitude and structural architecture. Such simulations would provide a mechanistic link between the inferred Ising-like parameters and real-time trajectories.

Beyond static architecture, our results open avenues for investigating the temporal stabilization of social structures. Specifically, whether the robust emergence of asymmetry (\mathcal{X}_{12}) follows a learning curve or represents an immediate response to spatial constraints remains an open question. Integrating entropy production measures could further reveal the metabolic efficiency gained by transitioning from boundary-driven to network-dominated navigation.

V. CONCLUSION

Our study reveals that confined minimal active groups exhibit systematic architectural changes with increasing size. By applying an inverse asymmetric Ising model to the trajectories of *Neocaridina davidi*, we demonstrated

that group size is encoded through two orthogonal physical channels: the global coupling scale and the internal interaction architecture.

A key finding is the statistical orthogonality between the structural features defining group identity (\mathcal{X}_2 , \mathcal{X}_{12}) and the primary axis of correlated variation (PC_1). This decoupling implies that collective identity is robustly embedded in the low-variance architectural dispersion of the network. This property remains independent of the high-amplitude statistical volatility that characterizes the overall scale of coordination.

We identified a distinct progression in the network organization: from simple coordination in pairs to structurally frustrated triplets, and finally to strongly nonreciprocal collectives at $N = 4$. This regime represents the maximal tractable state for isolating the core interaction motifs that seed coordinated steady states before kinetic arrest at higher occupancy ($N \geq 5$) obscures the underlying coordination rules. These shifts drive a spectral compression that amplifies global order while simultaneously lowering the statistical barriers between configuration modes. This spectral “crowding” results in a broader repertoire of accessible states, allowing the collective to maintain dynamical flexibility despite high global stiffness.

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Data Availability The data supporting this study’s findings are summarized within the article, its Appendices, and its Supplemental Material. Processed feature statistics, measures, and transformations (X_1 – X_{12}) are presented in the respective tables and figures. A representative experimental video of the $N = 4$ shrimp system is provided as Supplemental Material [16]. Raw trajectory data, tracking scripts, and analysis code are available from the corresponding author upon reasonable request.

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Appendix A: Experimental and Tracking Details

This appendix supports the methodology described in Sec. II A and Sec. II B by providing the full technical and computational specifications.

1. Apparatus and Environmental Control

The circular soda–lime glass Petri dishes had a diameter of 100 mm and a depth of 10 mm. To suppress optical transmission, the outer bottom surface was coated with

a matte 100 μm white PVC film, and the sidewall was covered with opaque tape to minimize reflections. Each dish contained 70 mL of conditioned water maintained at $(22.0 \pm 0.5)^\circ\text{C}$ and $\text{pH } 7.5 \pm 0.2$.

Uniform illumination was provided by a 10 W LED source placed 180 mm beneath the dish. Video was recorded at 1920×1080 pixels and 60 fps using a camera mounted 170 mm above the surface. Each trial lasted 10 min, yielding 36 000 frames. Shrimp (body length (10 ± 1) mm) were acclimated for 30 min in 30 L aquaria and allowed to stabilize in the experimental arena before recording. The arena dimensions were selected to ensure that all individuals remained within the typical sensory range of their conspecifics, guaranteeing that the inferred network effectively represents the full interaction space. All statistical analyses were performed on the nonequilibrium steady state, confirmed by the stability of radial distributions over the recording duration.

2. Computer Vision and Software Architecture

The *idtracker.ai* algorithm was trained on 200 manually annotated frames (100 contact, 100 non-contact). The entire tracking pipeline was managed by a custom C++/WinUI3 program utilizing the OpenCV 4.12 library. This software pre-processed video data, prepared parameters, and executed tracking in batch mode (~ 7 min/video on an Nvidia RTX 4070).

Head-orientation detection was performed via `cv2.fitEllipse` on thresholded binary contours. Object tracking relied on background subtraction and contour segmentation. For data quality assurance, an interactive visualization allowed for manual trajectory correction via interpolation.

Appendix B: Algorithms Summary

The methodology relies on two core algorithms to ensure the stability and robustness of the inferred physical parameters. The first, Parameter estimation (Algorithm 1), is an intensive statistical fitting procedure built around bootstrapping to determine the optimal coupling parameters (\mathbf{J}) and external fields (\mathbf{h}) for the Asymmetric Ising Model. This process repeatedly draws multiple subsamples of the raw trajectory data (\mathcal{T}) to perform the fit, employing the L-BFGS-B optimization technique to minimize the penalized objective function. This yields a distribution of parameters rather than a single point estimate. The second algorithm, Feature Extraction and Validation (Algorithm 2), transforms these inferred parameters into the final results and validates the model’s performance. It calculates the 13 quantitative features (\mathcal{X}_m) describing the interaction structure, such as mean coupling strength, nonreciprocity, and spectral characteristics.

Algorithm 1: Parameter estimation

Input : Set of Trials $\mathcal{T} = \{\mathcal{T}^{(i)}\}$, Ensemble size N_{sub} , Subsample fraction γ_L , Regularization λ_{L2}

Output : Inferred Parameters $\Theta = \{\Theta^{(i,j)}\}_{i,j}$

Determine subsample size $T_{L\text{sub}} = \lceil \gamma_L \cdot T_{L\text{uni}} \rceil$;

for trial $i = 1$ to N_{trial} **do**

for subsample $j = 1$ to N_{sub} **do**

 Construct $\mathcal{T}^{(i,j)}$ by randomly sampling $T_{L\text{sub}}$ frames from $\mathcal{T}^{(i)}$ with replacement;

 Estimate $\Theta^{(i,j)}$ by minimizing Eq. (5) using the L-BFGS-B algorithm;

Algorithm 2: Feature Extraction and Validation

Input : Parameters $\Theta^{(i,j)}$, data $\mathcal{T}^{(i,j)}$

Output : Features $\mathcal{X}_m^{(i,j)}$

for trial i , subsample j **do**

 Compute $\mathcal{X}_1^{(i,j)}$ to $\mathcal{X}_{13}^{(i,j)}$ (Eqs. (7)–(19));

 Compute trial-level means $\bar{\mathcal{X}}_m^{(i)}$ and group-level means $\langle \mathcal{X}_m \rangle_N$;

Appendix C: Nonparametric Analysis of Group Size Discriminability

We employed nonparametric testing to reliably assess the discriminative power of the 12 structural features relative to the group-size identity. The robustness of this approach stems from its independence from assumptions of normality and homoscedasticity.

To evaluate whether feature distributions differ across the three group sizes, we utilized a hierarchical approach. First, the Kruskal-Wallis H-test was applied to establish global separation among all group sizes (Table IV). Where global significance was confirmed, Dunn’s post-hoc test with Bonferroni correction was subsequently used to resolve specific pairwise contrasts (Table V).

All 12 features retained for analysis were confirmed to differ significantly across the three group sizes ($p < 0.001$). The magnitude of the H-statistic, which quantifies the degree of separation between distributions, identifies the most potent discriminators as ranked in Table IV.

The feature \mathcal{X}_{12} exhibits the most robust discriminative

Feature	H-Statistic	p-value	Rank
\mathcal{X}_{12}	91261.26	$< 10^{-100}$	1st
\mathcal{X}_2	80335.16	$< 10^{-100}$	2nd
\mathcal{X}_3	22695.78	$< 10^{-100}$	3rd
\mathcal{X}_9	20189.54	$< 10^{-100}$	4th
\mathcal{X}_{10}	18590.29	$< 10^{-100}$	5th

Table IV: Top 5 structural features ranked by the Kruskal-Wallis H -statistic for $\gamma_L = 1$. The ranking confirms the predictive hierarchy identified by supervised ensemble models, with nonreciprocal asymmetry (\mathcal{X}_{12}) and interaction heterogeneity (\mathcal{X}_2) serving as the primary discriminators across group sizes.

Feature	$N = 2$ vs $N = 3$	$N = 2$ vs $N = 4$	$N = 3$ vs $N = 4$
	(p)	(p)	(p)
\mathcal{X}_{12}	$< 10^{-100}$	$< 10^{-100}$	$< 10^{-100}$
\mathcal{X}_2	$< 10^{-100}$	$< 10^{-100}$	1.55×10^{-74}
\mathcal{X}_3	$< 10^{-100}$	1.52×10^{-235}	$< 10^{-100}$
\mathcal{X}_9	$< 10^{-100}$	$< 10^{-100}$	$< 10^{-100}$
\mathcal{X}_{10}	$< 10^{-100}$	$< 10^{-100}$	$< 10^{-100}$

Table V: Dunn’s post-hoc test p -values (Bonferroni corrected) resolving pairwise contrasts following the established global Kruskal-Wallis significance for the top 5 discriminators at $\gamma_L = 1$. These results statistically validate the “primary triad” (\mathcal{X}_2 , \mathcal{X}_{12} , \mathcal{X}_3) identified by ensemble classifiers as the system’s structural backbone. While \mathcal{X}_{12} , \mathcal{X}_9 , and \mathcal{X}_{10} maintain absolute separation across all N , the interaction heterogeneity (\mathcal{X}_2) exhibits a measured statistical saturation at the $N = 3 \rightarrow 4$ boundary. This confirms that the universal hierarchy observed in machine learning is rooted in robust, nonparametric statistical differences.

power, maintaining highly significant differences across all three pairwise comparisons. Furthermore, \mathcal{X}_2 serves as an effective discriminator for all pairs, with even its smallest divergence—observed between the $N = 3$ and $N = 4$ groups—remaining statistically profound ($p \approx 10^{-74}$). This concentration of group-size identity within a minimalist subset of structural features confirms that nonreciprocal asymmetry (\mathcal{X}_{12}) and interaction heterogeneity (\mathcal{X}_2) establish the definitive statistical foundation for the collective’s architectural core.

Appendix D: Null-model validation of nonreciprocal asymmetry

To distinguish the biological origin of nonreciprocal interactions from numerical noise, we implement a parametric bootstrap null-model test. This procedure is integrated with the temporal decorrelation and ensemble subsampling detailed in Sec. II C 1. The test functions by generating synthetic datasets from a strictly symmetric version of the inferred interactions, thereby establishing a *symmetric shadow* of the biological collective. By reapplying the inference pipeline to these synthetic samples, we identify the baseline nonreciprocal asymmetry \mathcal{X}_{12} that arises solely from finite-size sampling effects. This baseline represents the sampling noise floor, providing a rigorous benchmark against which the empirical nonreciprocity is evaluated.

The core philosophy of this approach is to construct an empirical distribution of the nonreciprocal asymmetry via bootstrapping a single experimental replicate and compare it against its symmetric shadow—an equilibrium counterpart that preserves interaction heterogeneity \mathcal{X}_2 but enforces detailed balance. To ensure statistical robustness, the methodology relies on a hierarchical nested aggregation structure that explicitly separates biological variability from finite-sample effects. The hierarchy is de-

fined as follows: first, we generate $N_{\text{sub}} = 200$ bootstrap realizations to estimate the internal variance of a single replicate (Level 1: intra-replicate bootstrap). Due to the significant computational overhead of nested synthetic sequence generation and subsequent re-inference—which required high-performance computing facilities—this ensemble size was selected as a robust yet feasible limit for the null-model test. Second, we aggregate these results across $N_{\text{trial}} = 8$ independent experimental replicates to form a representative population for each group size (Level 2: multi-replicate ensemble). Third, we contrast these ensembles across $N \in \{2, 3, 4\}$ to establish the structural signature of the collective (Level 3: cross-size identity). Finally, to prove that this identity is a persistent physical signal rather than a numerical artifact, we validate the entire hierarchy across data fractions $\gamma_L \in \{0.5, 1.0\}$.

a. Parametric Bootstrap Procedure. To statistically evaluate the MaxEnt null model, we employ a parametric bootstrap approach. For every bootstrap realization \mathcal{D}_k ($k \in \{1, \dots, N_{\text{sub}}\}$) processed at Level 1, we perform parallel inference across two branches under strictly identical algorithmic conditions. In the empirical branch, the parameters $\{\mathbf{J}_k, \mathbf{h}_k\}$ are estimated by minimizing the L_2 -regularized negative log-pseudolikelihood as defined in Eq. (5), from which we derive the nonreciprocal asymmetry feature $\mathcal{X}_{12,k}$ (Eq. (18)) and the empirical distribution \mathcal{P}_{emp} with mean μ_{12}^{emp} . In the synthetic branch, we construct a MaxEnt null model. For every inferred matrix \mathbf{J}_k , we define its symmetric equivalent as $\mathbf{J}_k^{\text{sym}} = \frac{1}{2}(\mathbf{J}_k + \mathbf{J}_k^{\text{T}})$, representing the conservative part of the effective effective cost function (Eq. (6)). From $\mathbf{J}_k^{\text{sym}}$ we generate a synthetic dataset \mathcal{D}'_k using a Gibbs sampler (burn-in: 1000 MCS, thinning: 20 MCS). This dataset is fed back into the identical inference pipeline to obtain the null matrix \mathbf{J}'_k and the feature $\mathcal{X}'_{12,k}$. This yields the null distribution $\mathcal{P}_{\text{null}}$ representing the spurious asymmetry expected from an equilibrium system with identical statistics. Any systematic bias introduced by the regressor is thereby present in both branches and cancels in the final Z -score.

b. Statistical Assessment and Robustness. The significance of the observed nonreciprocity for a specific replicate m is quantified by the Z -score: $Z_m = (\mu_{12}^{\text{emp}} - \mu_{12}^{\text{null}})/\sigma_{12}^{\text{null}}$, where μ_{12}^{null} and $\sigma_{12}^{\text{null}}$ are the mean and standard deviation (SD) of $\mathcal{P}_{\text{null}}$. These individual Z_m scores characterize the robustness of each biological replicate. Our results, summarized in Table VI, reveal a nonlinear increase in significance as a function of group size N . While for $N = 2, 3$ the mean Z remains near zero, a strong directional signal emerges at $N = 4$ (Level 3). The subsequent validation across data fractions shows that the mean Z increases from 30.58 ($\gamma_L = 0.5$) to 43.27 ($\gamma_L = 1.0$), closely following the $\sqrt{\gamma_L}$ dependence expected for a persistent structural signal. The high standard deviation of Z and the stable significance rate of 87.5% indicate that the drive for nonreciprocal interactions is statistically dominant at $N = 4$, yet subject to inter-replicate heterogeneity. A single realization remains a consistent outlier, appearing indistinguishable from the

null model—a detail preserved by our nested aggregation framework.

Table VI: Statistical summary of nonreciprocity tests (Z -scores) for different group sizes N and data fractions γ_L .

γ_L	N	Mean Z	SD Z	Min	Max	Sig. Rate
0.5	2	-0.03	0.20	-0.24	0.39	0.0%
	3	0.06	0.21	-0.27	0.33	0.0%
	4	30.58	36.01	0.54	106.47	87.5%
1.0	2	0.01	0.18	-0.20	0.40	0.0%
	3	-0.02	0.25	-0.46	0.25	0.0%
	4	43.27	55.30	0.65	157.74	87.5%

Appendix E: Supplementary Tables: Feature Importance, PCA Loadings

This appendix presents the full numerical results supporting the analyses in Section III. Table VII reports feature importance scores from the RF and GB classifiers. Table VIII lists loadings of the first two principal components.

Appendix F: Complementary Analysis: Hierarchical Clustering (UPGMA)

Hierarchical Clustering (UPGMA) was performed on the 12 scaled features to complement the PCA and non-parametric tests. The clustering process utilizes the Eu-

Feature (\mathcal{X}_m)	RF Importance	GB Importance
\mathcal{X}_2	0.2724	0.4686
\mathcal{X}_{12}	0.2401	0.2934
\mathcal{X}_3	0.1584	0.1591
\mathcal{X}_7	0.0538	0.0004
\mathcal{X}_9	0.0530	0.0067
\mathcal{X}_4	0.0451	0.0189
\mathcal{X}_1	0.0378	0.0000
\mathcal{X}_{10}	0.0348	0.0117
\mathcal{X}_{11}	0.0342	0.0015
\mathcal{X}_5	0.0316	0.0051
\mathcal{X}_6	0.0204	0.0180
\mathcal{X}_8	0.0184	0.0166

Table VII: Feature importance scores from RF and GB classifiers for $\gamma_L = 1$. Based on an aggregated global ranking, results identify three categories: (i) a primary triad ($\mathcal{X}_2, \mathcal{X}_{12}, \mathcal{X}_3$) with absolute stability across bagging and boosting architectures, where the top two alone account for $\approx 76\%$ of the GB weight; (ii) an intermediate regime ($\mathcal{X}_4, \mathcal{X}_{10}, \mathcal{X}_9$); and (iii) a set of residual descriptors ($\mathcal{X}_1, \mathcal{X}_5, \mathcal{X}_6, \mathcal{X}_7, \mathcal{X}_8, \mathcal{X}_{11}$). This universal hierarchy identifies the top triad as the intrinsic structural backbone of the system, independent of the specific learning paradigm.

Feature (\mathcal{X}_m)	PC ₁ Loading	PC ₂ Loading
\mathcal{X}_1	0.3913	-0.1820
\mathcal{X}_2	0.1154	0.4585
\mathcal{X}_3	-0.0158	-0.3427
\mathcal{X}_4	0.1558	-0.3809
\mathcal{X}_5	-0.3613	0.1300
\mathcal{X}_6	0.0007	0.3021
\mathcal{X}_7	0.3628	0.2896
\mathcal{X}_8	0.3532	0.0395
\mathcal{X}_9	0.3471	0.2683
\mathcal{X}_{10}	0.3852	-0.0948
\mathcal{X}_{11}	0.3883	-0.2002
\mathcal{X}_{12}	0.0499	0.4238

Table VIII: Loadings of the first two principal components (PC₁ and PC₂) for $\gamma_L = 1$. (PC₁) represents global interaction scale and volatility, while PC₂ encodes group-size identity via interaction heterogeneity (\mathcal{X}_2) and nonreciprocity (\mathcal{X}_{12}).

Step	Cluster 1	Cluster 2	Distance	Size
1	\mathcal{X}_1	\mathcal{X}_{11}	26.92	2
2	\mathcal{X}_{10}	$\{\mathcal{X}_1, \mathcal{X}_{11}\}$	154.99	3
3	\mathcal{X}_7	\mathcal{X}_9	202.96	2
4	\mathcal{X}_8	$\{\mathcal{X}_1, \mathcal{X}_{10}, \mathcal{X}_{11}\}$	222.53	4
5	\mathcal{X}_2	$\{\mathcal{X}_7, \mathcal{X}_9\}$	295.11	3
6	$\{\mathcal{X}_1, \mathcal{X}_8, \mathcal{X}_{10}, \mathcal{X}_{11}\}$	$\{\mathcal{X}_2, \mathcal{X}_7, \mathcal{X}_9\}$	360.18	7
7	\mathcal{X}_6	\mathcal{X}_{12}	394.74	2
8	\mathcal{X}_3	\mathcal{X}_4	429.07	2
9	\mathcal{X}_5	$\{\mathcal{X}_6, \mathcal{X}_{12}\}$	447.88	3
10	$\{\mathcal{X}_{1,2,7,8,9,10,11}\}$	$\{\mathcal{X}_3, \mathcal{X}_4\}$	473.43	9
11	$\{\mathcal{X}_5, \mathcal{X}_6, \mathcal{X}_{12}\}$	$\{\mathcal{X}_{1,2,3,4,7,8,9,10,11}\}$	520.92	12

Table IX: UPGMA linkage matrix (average linkage, Euclidean distance) for the 12 scaled features. Each step represents the merging of two clusters, where lower step numbers indicate higher similarity. Steps 1–6 define the magnitude-related mega-cluster ($\mathcal{X}_1, \mathcal{X}_7, \dots, \mathcal{X}_{11}$), confirming high redundancy among bulk statistical measures. In contrast, the structural triad ($\mathcal{X}_2, \mathcal{X}_{12}, \mathcal{X}_3$) remains fragmented into separate branches until the final merging stage (Step 11, distance 520.92). This topology confirms that the system’s group-size identity is encoded in distinct, nonredundant architectural features rather than in the correlated variation of the global cost function scale.

clidean distance between feature vectors, offering an alternative perspective on feature similarity based on absolute profile, distinct from the linear correlation measured by PCA.

The process is fully defined by the linkage matrix, which details the sequence of cluster formation and the corresponding merge distance. Table IX presents the most relevant steps of the linkage matrix.

The UPGMA results show that features associated with group-size identity ($\mathcal{X}_2, \mathcal{X}_{12}, \mathcal{X}_3$) do not form clusters at low distances, reflecting their distinct physical origins. Specifically, the fraction of negative couplings (\mathcal{X}_3) clusters with boundary-induced biases (\mathcal{X}_4) only at Step 8

Figure 8: UPGMA dendrogram showing hierarchical clustering of features based on Euclidean distance for $\gamma_L = 1$. The branching architecture visually confirms that the primary predictive triad ($\mathcal{X}_2, \mathcal{X}_{12}, \mathcal{X}_3$) does not cluster at low distances. Instead, these features remain isolated in separate sub-trees until the final stages of the hierarchy (distance > 400), demonstrating that the nonequilibrium structural identity is encoded in mutually independent feature profiles rather than redundant stochastic descriptors.

Features (\mathcal{X}_m)	Acc.	AIC	BIC
\mathcal{X}_2	0.5870	119549.91	119588.69
\mathcal{X}_{12}	0.6598	122713.39	122752.17
\mathcal{X}_{11}	0.5988	229117.52	229156.30
\mathcal{X}_1	0.5506	235468.68	235507.46
\mathcal{X}_7	0.5428	236849.57	236888.35

Table X: Performance of top single-feature MLR models ($n_p = 1$) using globally standardized features. Updated with new ensemble data. Note: \mathcal{X}_{12} shows higher accuracy, but \mathcal{X}_2 remains the most parsimonious according to BIC.

(429.07), while interaction heterogeneity (\mathcal{X}_2) joins the global scale cluster at Step 5. In contrast, magnitude-related features ($\mathcal{X}_1, \mathcal{X}_7\text{--}\mathcal{X}_{11}$) coalesce into a cohesive mega-cluster by Step 6 (360.18), confirming their high redundancy. The fact that the primary predictive triad remains fragmented until the final merge (Step 11, 520.92) reinforces the conclusion that these features provide complementary information about the system’s nonequilibrium interaction architecture.

Appendix G: Complementary MLR Data

This appendix contains the numerical output supporting the MLR analysis presented in Section III E. All models were fit on globally standardized (Z-scored) features; reported coefficients have been back-transformed to the original physical scale (see Section III E).

a. Information Criteria Definitions: We report two information criteria for model comparison. The *Akaike Information Criterion* (AIC) estimates prediction error, balancing model fit against complexity. The *Bayesian Information Criterion* (BIC) adds a stronger penalty for additional parameters, favoring more parsimonious mod-

Rank	Features (\mathcal{X}_m)	Accuracy	BIC
1	$(\mathcal{X}_2, \mathcal{X}_{12})$	0.9908	11411.49
2	$(\mathcal{X}_1, \mathcal{X}_9)$	0.9194	32621.11
3	$(\mathcal{X}_9, \mathcal{X}_{11})$	0.9166	33908.69
4	$(\mathcal{X}_7, \mathcal{X}_{11})$	0.8746	62151.16
5	$(\mathcal{X}_2, \mathcal{X}_7)$	0.8163	83462.80
6	$(\mathcal{X}_1, \mathcal{X}_7)$	0.7830	95127.53

Table XI: Ranking of the top-performing two-feature MLR models. The model combining interaction heterogeneity (\mathcal{X}_2) and nonreciprocal asymmetry (\mathcal{X}_{12}) emerges as the superior discriminator with near-perfect accuracy and the lowest BIC. This confirms that the collective’s structural architecture encodes group size more effectively than bulk statistical or spectral magnitudes.

els. Lower values of both criteria indicate better trade-offs between fit and complexity.

b. Table X: Single-Feature Model Performance This table ranks the top five single-feature models by BIC, providing the benchmark against which two-feature models are compared. The feature \mathcal{X}_2 (interaction heterogeneity) remains the most parsimonious single predictor, though all single-feature models exhibit accuracy (< 0.66) inadequate for reliable classification.

c. Table XI: Top Two-Feature Model Ranking This table presents the best-performing two-feature models

(without interaction terms) ranked by BIC. The results confirm the superior status of the structural pairing $(\mathcal{X}_2, \mathcal{X}_{12})$, which achieves near-perfect classification accuracy (0.9908) with the overall lowest BIC by a substantial margin. While the minimal spectral model $(\mathcal{X}_9, \mathcal{X}_{11})$ remains highly predictive, it is significantly outperformed by the combination of interaction heterogeneity and non-reciprocal asymmetry. This outcome establishes that the nonequilibrium architectural features identified in our prior UPGMA and PCA analyses are indeed the primary determinants of group-size identity.

d. Table XII: Standardized Coefficient Vectors This table consolidates the coefficient matrices for the three key models discussed in the main text. The coefficients are reported in standardized form (Z-score units), allowing for a direct comparison of the relative importance of each feature in determining the log-odds of the group-size identity relative to the $N = 4$ reference class.

e. Supplementary Note: Interaction Model Analysis We evaluated models with pairwise interaction terms for all feature combinations. For the spectral feature pair $(\mathcal{X}_9, \mathcal{X}_{11})$, the interaction model provided a minimal reduction in BIC compared to the non-interaction version. However, the interaction coefficient remained statistically negligible ($|\gamma_{z,9 \times 11}| \approx 0$), suggesting that a linear combination of the structural features is sufficient to capture the group-size identity.

Model Type	Coefficient	$\gamma_{N=2}$ (std.)	$\gamma_{N=3}$ (std.)
Best Single-Feature (\mathcal{X}_2)	Intercept	0.4626	0.4877
	\mathcal{X}_2	-26.3664	-26.2990
Best Structural ($\mathcal{X}_2 + \mathcal{X}_{12}$)	Intercept	-6.0108	-0.5630
	\mathcal{X}_2	-18.7313	2.6958
	\mathcal{X}_{12}	-19.0517	-29.1301
Minimal Spectral ($\mathcal{X}_9 + \mathcal{X}_{11}$)	Intercept	4.0971	7.0518
	\mathcal{X}_9	-20.7414	-11.8842
	\mathcal{X}_{11}	24.9532	14.7834

Table XII: Standardized coefficient vectors $\gamma_{z,m}$ for the three primary multinomial logistic regression (MLR) models. The coefficients represent the relative contribution of each feature to the log-odds of the group-size identity relative to the $N = 4$ reference class. High absolute values indicate robust statistical separation between the collective states. Standardized units (Z -scores) allow for direct comparison across different architectural features. Coefficients are standardized to allow direct comparison of feature magnitudes across different physical dimensions.